

Process optimization for the production of citric acid by solid state fermentation using *Aspergillus flavus*

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Abstract

Citric acid was identified in lemons. Since citric acid is an intermediary of the ubiquitous citric acid cycle, it is found in all living things. Because of its pleasant taste and palatability, citric acid is used to flavor jams, jellies, sweets, desserts, frozen fruits, soft drinks, and wine. Citric acid brightens and protects food flavors as an antioxidant. 2007). The chemical business uses it as an antifoam agent, and the pharmaceutical sector uses trisodium citrate as a blood preservative. *Aspergillus niger*, a key industrial microbiology fungal, has been utilized to make citric acid for decades. Global demand for citric acid is rising faster than production, requiring more cost-effective methods. *Aspergillus niger*, a key industrial microbiology fungal, has been utilized to make citric acid for decades. Global demand for citric acid is rising faster than production, requiring more cost-effective methods. The most prevalent citric acid producer is *Aspergillus niger*. *Aspergillus niger* strains dominate citric acid production in labs and factories (Boominathan et al., 2012). Using an alternative organism can produce citric acid with consistently high yields and cheap raw ingredients, making the method economically viable.

Indian bio-based economies could benefit from sugarcane bagasse. Bagasse is the dry pulpy fibrous residue remaining after crushing sugarcane or sorghum stalks for juice. Many studies have employed sugarcane bagasse for solid-state fermentation to make citric acid. In this study we have optimized the fermentation different parameters to yield a maximum production using *Aspergillus flavus* strain. These results suggest that pretreated bagasse can be used to manufacture citric acid efficiently and cheaply. A pilot design for large-scale production can be realized using the improved production process. Bagasse can be used to make citric acid, reducing landfill waste and environmental damage

Keyword – Solid State Fermentation, Citric Acid, *Aspergillus Flavus*, Fungal Fermentation

Introduction

It was discovered that lemons contain citric acid. Since we now understand that citric acid is a component of the widespread citric acid cycle, all living things contain it. Although lemons, which naturally contain 7–9% citric acid, were once the primary source of citric acid, today microbiological fermentation accounts for nearly all of the world's citric acid production. Citric acid is used as a flavoring agent in a variety of foods and beverages, including desserts, frozen fruits, wine, jelly, jams, and candies. This is because of its pleasant taste and palatability. As an antioxidant and flavor preserver, citric acid does more than just make foods look brighter (Berovic, et al., 2007). It serves as an antifoam agent in the chemical industry and as a blood preservative in the pharmaceutical sector under the name trisodium citrate. (F.A. Steinbock and others, 1991). Through an active glycolytic pathway, a wide variety of microorganisms are capable of producing citric acid. Oxaloacetate and acetyl CoA condense to form citrate through the action of citrate synthase. In actuality, citrate inhibits glycolysis; however, positive effectors of the phosphofructokinase gene can reverse this inhibition. (PFK-(Kristensen et al., 1979; Kappeli et al., 1978). Because of the "ammonium pool" phenomenon, which prevents the enzyme phosphofructokinase from working, fructose and glucose are converted to pyruvate, which accelerates glycolysis and the production of citric acid.

The ability to produce citric acid has been assessed in a range of fungi. Numerous fungal strains, including *Aspergillus niger*, *A. awamori*, *A. fumigatus*, *A. phoenicis*, *A. lanosus*, *A. flavus*, *P. restrictum*, *Trichoderma viride*, *Mucor piriformis*, and *Ustilina vulgaris*, have been observed to accumulate citric acid in their culture media. For a long time, the commercial production of citric acid has relied on *Aspergillus niger*, one of the most significant fungi utilized in industrial microbiology. There needs to be a more cost-effective method of producing citric acid because global demand is outpacing supply. Yadegary and associates (2013). The most popular use of *niger* is in the manufacturing of citric acid. In terms of citric acid production on an industrial scale and in laboratory settings, *Aspergillus niger* strains have proven to be the most dominant (Boominathan et al., 2012). The inexpensive raw materials used to produce citric acid, along with the alternative organism's high and consistent yields, can make the process economically viable. Natural citric acid, which can be found in foods like oranges, lemons, and limes, functions as an antioxidant and shields cells from harm from free radicals. Citric acid may therefore be somewhat helpful in preventing heart disease, cancer, and other illnesses linked to cellular deterioration by free radicals. Furthermore, it may aid in the prevention of kidney stones and contribute to the maintenance of healthy pH levels in the body due to its alkalizing properties. Moreover, citric acid aids in the absorption of nutrients; this is why citric acid is included in many mineral supplements.

In India, sugarcane bagasse holds great potential as a biomass source for the transition to a bio-based economy. The dry, pulpy, fibrous residue left over after the stalks of sugarcane or sorghum are crushed to release their juice is called bagasse. A typical chemical analysis of dried and cleaned bagasse shows that 45–55% of it is composed of cellulose. 20–25% hemicellulose Lignin 18–24% Ash 1–4%. It is utilized as a biofuel to generate electricity, heat, and energy as well as to make pulp and building materials. Kumar et al. (2003) and Vandenberghe et al. (2000)

are just two of many studies that found sugarcane bagasse to be an effective substrate for solid-state fermentation in the production of citric acid.

The primary goal of this research is to quantify the concentration and yield of citric acid produced from sugar cane bagasse through solid-state fermentation with *Aspergillus flavus*. This will help evaluate its viability as an inexpensive citric acid source for future industrial applications and economic growth.

Figure 1.0 - Fermentation layout diagram for the industrial production of citric acid.

Materials and Methods

1. Sample Collection

The local vendors in Ballarpur city's central market were approached to collect sugar cane bagasse, which was packaged in paper foil. After being gathered, the bagasse was cleaned with water and sun-dried for two to three days. The dried bagasse was ground to a particle size of 2-3 mm and stored in moisture-free sealing bags.

Figure 2.0- A) Raw sugar cane bagasse collected in paper foil from the local vendors. B) Dried and grinded bagasse sample C) Sample collection area.

2. Culture Used

The *Aspergillus flavus* pure culture (NCIM 1028) was procured from the Department of Microbiology, Guru Nanak College of Science, Ballarpur MS-India). On a potato dextrose agar slant, the culture was grown, and it was stored at 4 degrees Celsius. Subcultures were performed every two weeks.

3. Inoculum Preparation

Before making the inoculum, the fungal conidia were taken from a culture that had been in the lab for five days. In 10 milliliters of sterile fermentation medium, a loopful of fungal spores was used to inoculate the medium. (Jin Woo and others, 2013).

4. Pretreatment of Substrate

Using diluted 1N HCl, the bagasse was gently pretreated. In a water bath set at 90°C for one hour, combine 10 gm of substrate with 100 ml of solution (10% w/v). After cooling, the substrate was then cleaned with distilled water. This is followed by drying it in an oven set to 100°C to extract any remaining moisture.

Figure 3.0- A) Bagasse pretreated with 1N HCl B) Moisture free dried pretreated bagasse.

5. Fermentation Media

In a conical flask, 30 grams of pretreated bagasse, 10 grams of NH_4NO_3 , 4.0 grams of K_2HPO_4 , 1.0 grams of MgSO_4 , and 2.0 grams of CaCO_3 were transferred to create the fermentation medium. The remaining volume was filled up to one liter with sterile distilled water. The flask was autoclaved for fifteen minutes at 121°C.

6. Study of effect of pH

In order to evaluate the correlation between microbial growth and metabolic processes, the pH of the fermentation medium was measured. A seven-day fermentation study was conducted to determine the effect of varying pH levels (ranging from 2 to 8) on maximum citric acid production. The media's initial pH was raised to 6.8.

7. Study of effect of temperature

Ensuring optimal production is dependent on temperature. It was investigated how various temperatures affected the amount of citric acid produced. Citric acid production was monitored at each of the five temperature points during the fermentation process, which lasted from 25 to 65 degrees Celsius.

8. Study of effect of incubation period

The relationship between citric acid production and fermentation period was investigated by running the fermentation process for various time periods ranging from 3 to 7 days. The flasks were kept in an orbital shaker for incubation. The citric acid yield was measured at the end of each incubation day.

9. Study of effect of substrate concentration

A range of substrate concentrations (1%, 2%, 3%, 4%, and 5%) were tested to determine how different concentrations affected citric acid production. After the substrate had been pretreated, a different concentration of the substrate was added to one liter of fermentation medium.

10. Study of effect of Nitrogen source

A variety of nitrogen sources, including ammonium sulfate, peptone, and urea (1 gm/100 ml), were tested to determine their impact on citric acid production. The amount of citric acid that was produced was measured after each flask was supplemented with a different nitrogen source.

11. Fermentation process

The 10 ml spore suspension from the slant culture was aseptically transferred to the production media, mixed, and then incubated at 30°C on an orbital shaker for five days at 200 RPM to ensure proper aeration. This was done for each flask that was to be used for parameter study. Periodically, every two days, the pH was measured. The experiment was carried out in a 500 mL conical flask. At various intervals, the fermented mixture fraction was collected. Every day, one flask was taken out to measure the amount of citric acid. We tested various process optimization factors to find the one that maximized citric acid production, including pH, temperature, incubation time, substrate concentration, and nitrogen source.

11. Detection of citric acid

Following the intended incubation time, three drops of Bromocresol green indicator were added to 10 milliliters of fermented distilled solution to measure the amount of citric acid produced. Acid can be detected by a change in color.

Figure 4.0 – A) Change in color after addition of bromocresol green indicate citric acid production B) Titration with 0.1N NaOH for detection of citric acid concentration.

12. Determination citric acid concentration

Citric acid concentration was determined using the titration method with 0.1 N NaOH and phenolphthalein as an indicator. Ten milliliters of distillate were used in the titration. The Socol et al., 2006 formula was used to calculate the concentration of citric acid as a percentage.

13. Recovery of citric acid

Filtration was used to separate the fungal mat and fermented broth once fermentation was complete. The fermented broth contains the citric acid. To precipitate the citric acid in the form of calcium citrate, $(Ca(OH)_2)$ was added to the fermented broth. After treating the precipitate with diluted H_2SO_4 , the insoluble calcium sulfate was precipitated, and the precipitate was filtered. By going through a carbon granule column, the precipitate solution's citric acid was refined. After filtering the solution, the pure citric acid crystal was obtained by evaporating it. (R.C. Dubey, 2003).

Result and Discussion

1. Pretreatment of substrate

When the substrates are collected, they are first heated in a water bath for one hour with 0.1 N HCL for pretreatment. Following this, they are washed and dried. Citric acid synthesis on pretreated and untreated substrate was examined. The amount of citric acid in the supernatant was measured after a five-day fermentation process. The results showed that pretreated substrate produced a citric acid concentration of 10.3 g/L, while untreated substrate produced 4.6 g/L. The outcomes agree with those of Khosravi et al. (2008), who found that pretreatment with diluted HCL led to the greatest production of citric acid. A good amount of citric acid was produced by the 2-3 mm size of substrate. The reason behind this is the high porosity, which leads to improved heat and mass transfer, ultimately leading to an increase in the production of citric acid. Kumar D. and others (2002).

Figure 5.0 – Comparison of citric acid production between treated and untreated bagasse substrate.

2. Effect of pH

The most crucial element for the healthy growth of fungal biomass is pH. Different pH values (2–8) were used for the fermentation reaction. Starting at a pH of 6.8, the pH gradually decreases to 3.0 on the eighth day of incubation. This process occurs at regular intervals. Concentrations of 8.7 g/L of citric acid were maximally produced in the pH range of 4 to 5. The pH gradually dropping is a sign that citric acid is being produced. D.V. Guebel et al. (2001). The pH of the medium should be around three to reduce the production of oxalic acid and gluconic acid. (H.S. Grewal and others, 1995). Research conducted by Abhishek S. et al. (2015) found that the optimal pH for extracting citric acid from sugar cane bagasse was 5.0.

Figure 6.0 – Showing the effect of different pH. Optimum pH 4.0 for the maximum production of citric acid was observed.

3. Effect of Temperature

The primary determinant of fungal growth and citric acid production is temperature. Various temperatures, including 25°C, 35°C, 45°, 55°C, and 65°C, were used to conduct the fermentation process. Every flask was incubated at a different temperature, and the concentration of citric acid was estimated using fermentation broth after a predetermined amount of time. At 35°C, the highest amount of citric acid (14.1 g/L) was produced. There appears to be an optimal temperature range for producing citric acid, though, and that is between 35 and 40 degrees Celsius. The amount of citric acid generated gradually decreases as the temperature rises further. Citric acid yield at 30°C is the maximum, according to Nwoba et al. (2015). Helen et al. (2014) discovered that the ideal temperature for a high level of citric acid production is 55°C. Low enzyme activity causes less production at low temperatures, and denaturation of citrate synthase at high temperatures reduces citric acid biosynthesis (T. E. Arzumanov et al., 2000). The type of substrate and organism used determines the temperature at which citric acid is produced.

Figure 7.0 – Showing the variation in temperature. The maximum production of citric acid was observed at 35°C. The optimum range of temperature was found to be 35°C to 40°C.

4. Effect of incubation period

To achieve a high yield of citric acid, various fermentation times were investigated. For 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 days, each flask containing the media and culture was incubated (Figure 4). After the specified amount of time had passed, the fermented broth was removed in order to measure the concentration of citric acid. It was discovered that the sixth day of the current study was ideal for producing the highest amount of citric acid (14.7 g/L). The fifth day of incubation was when the highest amount of citric acid was produced (Helen S. A. et al., 2014 and Kareem et al., 2010). The kind of substrate and the state of fermentation determine the ideal reaction time. Also, additional by-products like oxalic acid and enzyme catabolite repression accumulate during incubation, reducing production. (T. Panda and others, 1984). Citric acid production decreases as a result of a decrease in substrate nitrogen and sugar levels, according to some researchers (Y. D. Hang et al., 1986). As the incubation period and reducing sugar levels decrease, the fungal growth rate and citric acid production both increase relative to one another.

Figure 8.0 – Explains the effect of different incubation period. The highest concentration of citric acid (12.9 g/L) was obtained at 6th day.

5. Effect of Substrate Concentration

The impact of varying substrate concentrations on the synthesis of citric acid was investigated. A series of experiments were conducted using varying substrate concentrations, which ranged from 1% to 5%. Citric acid production in the fermented broth was measured after a predetermined amount of incubation. When substrate with a 3% substrate concentration was used, the maximum concentration of citric acid was found to be 16.7 g/L. The maximum yield of citric acid at this concentration could be attributed to increased substrate availability for the organism as well as sufficient heat and mass transfer. At a concentration of 2%, *Aspergillus niger* exhibited the maximum yield on fruit substrate. In 2014, Helen S.A. et al. The results presented here contradict those of Kareem et al. (2010), who determined that a sucrose concentration of 15% was optimal for citric acid production. Past research has shown that galactose and arabinose are sugars that hinder the production of citric acid. M. Hossain et al. (1985) found that citric acid production

could be supported by a substrate concentration of 3%, but that increasing the concentration beyond 3% would lead to higher levels of sugars in the pulp that inhibit citric acid production.

Figure 9.0 – Describe the effect of variation in the substrate concentration. The substrate concentration of 3% was found to be maximum for high yield of citric acid.

6. Effect of Nitrogen source

Since nitrogen is essential for metabolism and is a main component of both cells and enzymes, it is no surprise that it plays a significant role in the synthesis of citric acid. Arzumanov and associates, 2000. In order to investigate the impact of nitrogen, the fermentation medium was supplemented with varying concentrations of nitrogen sources, such as ammonium nitrate, peptone, and urea (0.5%, 1%, and 2%), and the concentration of citric acid was measured following the intended incubation period. At 1% ammonium nitrate, a high yield of citric acid (12.3 g/L) was achieved. Ammonium nitrate reduces synthesis at low concentrations and increases fungal growth and sugar utilization at high concentrations while decreasing the amount of citric acid at low concentrations. Kel H. and associates, 1981. Using molasses substrate, another researcher obtained 15.2 g/L of citric acid with 0.25% ammonium sulphate and 14.7 g/L of citric acid with 0.5% ammonium chloride. Shetty, Varsha (2015). The maximum production (8.4 g/L) at 0.5% concentration was obtained when urea was used. At 1% concentration, a high level of citric acid production (6.3 g/L) was obtained in the case of peptone. In order to facilitate the production of citric acid, the consumption of ammonium compounds lowers pH. Consequently, these compounds are generally preferred.

Figure 10.0 – The study of effect of nitrogen sources clearly depicts the 1% of ammonium nitrate suitable for the production citric acid.

7. Fermentation with optimized condition and recovery

The optimal conditions for fermentation were established after determining the pH, temperature, incubation time, substrate concentration, and nitrogen source. Six days of incubation resulted in the highest amount of citric acid production. By adding Bromocresol green indicator to fermented media, which turns yellow, it was possible to detect the presence of citric acid (Figure 10). For recovery and purity determination, the fermented broth was distilled and the resulting distillate was collected according to the procedure described by Soccoll et al. (2006).

8. Conclusion

Citric acid, derived from a wide range of fungi, has tremendous applications in the food and pharmaceutical industries. In India, sugarcane bagasse holds great potential as a biomass source for the development of a bio-based economy. It has been demonstrated that sugarcane bagasse can be converted into citric acid, making it a viable and economical alternative substrate for large-scale citric acid production. The purpose of this work was to ascertain whether solid residues from food processing could be used as a substrate for the solid-state fermentation of *Aspergillus flavus* to produce citric acid. *Aspergillus flavus* can produce citric acid from bagasse as a carbon source, according to this study. Based on the results shown here, using pretreated bagasse to make citric acid can be an efficient and cost-effective option. A pilot design for the large-scale production can be implemented using the production process that has been optimized. Utilizing bagasse as a base for the industrial manufacture of citric acid can help alleviate the landfill problem and its negative effects on the environment.

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